

DAGM Mustererkennung 1994, Springer: Berlin
A New Depth from Focus Technique for
In Situ Determination
of Cell Concentration in Bioreactors

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14888

T. Scholz¹, B. Jähne², H. Suhr³, G. Wehnert⁴, P. Geissler¹, K. Schneider⁵

¹ Institute of Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg
Im Neuenheimer Feld 366, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany

² Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing (IWR),
University of Heidelberg,

Im Neuenheimer Feld 368, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany

³ Fachhochschule für Technik Mannheim
Speyerer Str. 4, D-68163 Mannheim, Germany

⁴ ABB Corporate Research Center Heidelberg
Speyerer Str. 4, D-69115 Heidelberg, Germany

⁵ Institute of Chemical Engineering, University of Hannover
Callienstr. 3, D-30167 Hannover, Germany

Abstract. A new depth-from-focus technique is introduced that requires only a single image to determine the distance of simple shaped objects from the focal plane. The technique has been applied to evaluate the concentration of cells in a bioreactor during a fermentation process. Since the low-intensity fluorescent light gathered by a light-amplifying camera results in images of low signal-to-noise ratio, an adaptive smoothing filter is used. A sharpness criterion derived from bandpass decomposition of the image in a Laplacian pyramid is used to define a virtual measuring volume. In this volume, process parameters such as cell concentration, cell size and intensity of cell fluorescence are evaluated. The technique is also suitable for other types of simple objects.

1 Introduction

Digital image processing is a rapidly evolving field with growing applications in science and engineering. In many of these applications full 3D-information about the scene would be a great advantage. But there is one basic problem of optical imaging: the loss of depth caused by the projection of a 3D-scene onto the 2D-image plane. Research in computer vision in the past twenty years has focused on paradigms such as shape from shading, shape from stereo, shape from texture and shape from motion to infer the lost information from 2D-imagery. Much less attention has been paid to the depth-from-focus paradigm. It is based on the simple fact that blur increases with the distance from the plane of focus.

Most depth-from-focus techniques use several images of the same scene taken with different camera adjustments to infer depth from the blurring in the images. Darell [1990], for instance, determines the depth of an object by searching for the maximum sharpness in a focus series. In contrast, Ens [1993] does not change the

focus of the camera but takes only two images with different apertures. These types of multi-image approaches have the general disadvantage that they cannot be applied to scenes with fast moving objects like cells floating in a rapidly mixed bioreactor. Pentland [1987] and Bove [1989] for instance used a setup with two cameras to get images of the same scene by using beam splitters.

Since multi-camera setups are more complicated to handle, the question arises whether the approach to the depth-from-focus problem with just one image is feasible. It is obvious that no general solution for this problem exists. Knowledge about the properties of the observed objects is a necessary requirement. In many applications however, the types of objects that occur are precisely known.

This paper focuses on a new approach for depth-from-focus using a single image by merging knowledge about shape and approximate size of objects with the depth-from-focus paradigm to determine depth in a scene. Suhr, Wehnert et al. [1990] describe a new method for online and in-situ determination of the cell concentration in bioreactors. Images of the cell suspension are made by means of a microscope immersed in the bioreactor. The measurement of the concentration is based on the selective counting of objects if they show a defined minimum-sharpness. Thus particles e.g. cells can be assigned to an optically defined sample volume, provided that they are sufficiently similar.

Cells build a class of objects that usually fullfills a number of prerequisites so that depth recovery from a single image is feasible. To realize this concept with automatic image processing and with a steam sterilizable optical setup, a cooperation between Asea Brown Boveri Corporate Research Center Heidelberg, the Institute of Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg and the Institute of Chemical Engineering, University of Hannover was established [Wehnert, Suhr et al, 1994].

In many biotechnical applications cell cultures require precise process control, homogeneity in the bioreactor and high sterility. So far, one of the most difficult assignments was to measure the cell concentration with an appropriate instrument under these conditions. A depth-from-focus sensor using image processing to measure the cell concentration has significant advantages over other techniques. The defocus of the cell is used to determine a virtual measuring volume from which absolute concentration can be inferred. This non-contact approach avoids all the disadvantages caused by mechanical volume delimiters, bypasses or taking samples. Living cells can be separated from dead cells and other objects such as bubbles or particles by using the fluorescence of the NAD(P)⁺H molecules of living cells as an indicator. In addition, the described setup allows the visualization of single cells. So it is possible to get information about their metabolism, cell activity and cell division stages.

2 Image Formation

The experiments were performed in cooperation with Schneider [1994] and Bitner at the Institute of Chemical Engineering at the University of Hannover.

First measurements were made in November 1993 with a culture of yeast cells (*saccharomyces cerevisiae*) in an experimental bioreactor (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Experimental bioreactor.

During the fermentation process all important process parameters such as temperature, velocity of the stirrer, pH value or oxygen concentration are monitored. The in situ depth-from-focus probe was inserted into a port of the bioreactor (Fig. 2). A microscope objective with a magnification of 100 and a numerical aperture of 0.95 was placed in front of the probe, separated from the interior of the reactor by a quartz slide cover. The cells were rapidly intermixed by a stirrer in the reactor. The illumination was made through the objective with a nitrogen laser at a wavelength of 337 nm and a pulse length of 3 ns. The maximum absorption wavelength of the NAD(P)H molecules is at 340 nm and the maximum emission wavelength is at 460 nm. Thus direct reflexes of the incoming illumination could be suppressed using a lowpass glass filter placed in front of the camera.

At regular intervals, an image was taken and stored on a laser video disk. The image formation and storage was synchronized with the laser pulses. Because of the weak fluorescence of the cells, it was necessary to use a light amplifying camera. Since NAD(P)H is an intermediate product of the metabolism of the cells, only living cells are imaged and errors in the determination of cell concentration caused by dead cells are avoided. The cells, having an average diameter of 5-6 μm , are imaged as circular objects with almost Gaussian shape and a small plateau in their center when they are near the focal plane. The imaging frequency was determined by the actual cell concentration to get an appropriate statistical amount of counted cells for each evaluated time interval.

In order to avoid quality loss of the images caused by the brightness of defocused cells between the probe and the plane of focus, the experimental setup was adjusted so that the focal plane had its place about 8 μm in front of the probe. To get a calibration of depth for the interpretation of the cell images, the identical optical setup was used to take a series of images of precisely shifted

standard particles. For this, latex particles with a similar shape and size as yeast cells were embedded in a gel and shifted with a positioning system in steps of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. This procedure allows to compute a calibration table which is used to evaluate the exact distance between the cells and the plane of focus.

Fig. 2: The in situ probe.

3 Image Preprocessing

Due to the fact that the illumination time is 3 ns, only one field of the interlaced 512×512 pixel frames was illuminated. The illuminated frame and half of the columns were taken to get a 256×256 frame for further evaluation. Aliasing and loss of information could be avoided because the optical resolution of the system was lower than half of the resolution of the camera. A plane of about $70 \times 70 \mu\text{m}$ was directly imaged by the objective.

The background image which is computed as the average of a series of the past 100 images is then subtracted. This is necessary to facilitate the segmentation of cells. The background brightness is caused by defocused cells and increases with higher cell concentration. It is not evenly distributed. An example, already interpolated and with its background subtracted is shown in Figure 3. This image is taken about 4 hours after the cultivation started and the cell concentration has reached just $\frac{1}{12}$ of its highest level. We see one very sharp and one blurred cell. Two other cells are almost out of focus. Because of the low-intensity fluorescence of the cells, the signal-to-noise ratio is very bad. Since the sharpness of the cells is our indicator for their depth it is not possible to use common smoothing filters to suppress noise. Thus in cooperation with Geissler [1993] an adaptive smoothing filter was implemented which is described in the following.

3.1 Adaptive Smoothing

The aim of adaptive smoothing is to preserve the sharpness of objects in the image. To achieve this aim, it is necessary to smooth only along but not across the lines of constant gray values. For that it is sufficient to know the direction of smallest variance of the gray values at each pixel.

Fig. 3: Typical cells at different distances from the focal plane.

In order to obtain this direction, the local orientation is calculated from the local variance in different directions. The local variance $Var_{\phi}[g(\mathbf{x})]$ of the gray values $g(\mathbf{x})$ in the direction ϕ is given by

$$Var_{\phi}[g(\mathbf{x})] = E_{\phi}[(g(\mathbf{x}) - E_{\phi}(g(\mathbf{x})))^2] \quad \text{with} \quad E_{\phi}[g(\mathbf{x})] = \int B_{\phi}(\lambda)g(\mathbf{x} + \lambda \mathbf{e}_{\phi})d\lambda$$

as the weighted average of g in ϕ direction, \mathbf{e}_{ϕ} is the unit vector and $B(\lambda)$ is a normalized weighting function. The local orientation is then obtained from the variances in different directions ϕ_i by the vector-addition technique [Knutsson and Granlund, 1983]. It can be shown that the use of four different directions with angles of 45° to each other results in a suitable accurateness of the calculation of the orientation direction ϕ .

The angle of the local orientation is then given by

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \arcc \left(\frac{Var_{\phi_0}[\rho(\mathbf{x})] - Var_{\phi_2}[\rho(\mathbf{x})]}{Var_{\phi_1}[\rho(\mathbf{x})] - Var_{\phi_3}[\rho(\mathbf{x})]} \right), \quad \phi_i = i \frac{\pi}{4}$$

With this information, it is possible to smooth along the contour lines of the objects in the image. So the course of a contour line through a pixel is evaluated for n pixels in both directions, considering an interpolation between the grid points and an amount of robustness to prevent a break out of the filter at departing

values [Geissler, 1993]. Then this segment of the contour line is smoothed by a common smoothing filter, for example a binomial filter.

Figure 4 shows the example image smoothed with the described method.

Fig. 4: The result of adaptive smoothing.

3.2 Segmentation

Subsequently the segmentation of the cells from the background is computed. It consists of three steps:

- Finding of the cells by a simple threshold as condition. Since we have subtracted the background at the beginning and removed the noise, it is possible to use this technique to obtain starting points for the next step.
- Segmentation of the cell with a region growing procedure
- Labeling of the cells by a standard floodfill procedure. With this algorithm each cell gets its own label and can be identified in the further steps of our evaluation.

Figure 5 shows the label image of our example.

Fig. 5: Labeled image.

3.3 Separation

We will see that it is necessary to evaluate each cell separately from the others to get its distance from the focal plane. So we have to evaluate the borderline for each cell in the label image and to compute a plane fit through the gray values of its border. After that, each cell is embedded in an own image and slightly smoothed between fitted plane and edge. The plane fit is computed by a least squares solution to the general linear model [Ott, 1977].

4 Depth-From-Focus

As we have already discussed, there is no general solution for the depth-from-focus problem. Knowledge about the observed objects and the optical setup is a necessary requirement to get the desired information. In our case, this knowledge is given by the fact that the used yeast cells are objects of approximately similar size and shape and that an identical optical setup with particles similar to the cells was taken to get the calibration series [Scholz, 1994].

To get the information about the distance between the cells and the plane of focus, a criterion is required from which the desired depth could be evaluated. It is obvious that increased blurring effects longer scales. Therefore a bandpass decomposition seems to be an appropriate tool. A well suited way to get such a decomposition with a multigrid data structure is the Laplacian pyramid [Burt, 1984]. The Laplacian pyramid is derived from the Gaussian pyramid by subtracting the smoothed from the unsmoothed image on each level. Therefore each level $L^{(P)}$ of the Laplacian pyramid is obtained by

$$L^{(P)} = G^{(P)} - \mathcal{E}^{(P+1)}G^{(P+1)} = [I^{(P+1)} - \mathcal{E}^{(P+1)}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{B})^{(P)}] \left(\prod_{p=0}^{P-1} (\mathcal{R}\mathcal{B})^{(p)} \right) G^{(0)}$$

with $G^{(0)}$ as the lowest level of the Gaussian pyramid which is the original image, \mathcal{B} as smoothing operator, the reduction operator \mathcal{R} and the expansion operator \mathcal{E} [Jaehne, 1993]. As result, only the fine scales, removed by the smoothing operation, remain in the finer level.

Now two more steps are needed for an appropriate depth criterion [Scholz, 1994]:

- First, the squares of the gray values are computed. This operation is performed at each level of the Laplacian pyramid and results in a sort of energy contents of the different scales in the image.
- Then we sum up all the values of a level and compute the ratios between the sums of different levels.

The sums of the squared values at each level of the Laplacian pyramid are used as feature vector. The ratios of different components of this vector can then be used as indicators for the depth of the regarding object. Thus cells with a variation in brightness can be evaluated.

To get the correct distance of a cell, we have to compare the ratios of the components of the feature vector with the ones of a calibration series using a standard particle. Figure 6 shows the ratios of the second and the third component to the first of such a series. Standard latex particles with $4.5\mu\text{m}$ diameter have been used which are very similar to yeast cells concerning shape and size.

Using a precise translation stage, latex particles embedded in gel were moved in z-direction in steps of $0.5\mu\text{m}$. The identical optical setup as used for the imaging of the cells was used to obtain this calibration series. It could be seen, that the ratios are almost symmetric around the focal plane and that the curves could be very well approximated by a Gaussian. It is, of course, not possible to differentiate between a particle in front of or behind the focal plane with this method. But this is not necessary to get the virtual measuring volume.

Fig. 6: The first two ratios of the feature vector components.

5 Results

The described method to get the depth from focus was tested successfully with some standard series. Furthermore during a 24-hour fermentation process about 25,000 images were stored with a laser video recorder and offline probes were taken. At the beginning of the cultivation an image was taken every 2 seconds, later this interval increased with the concentration of the cells up to 10 seconds.

Figure 7 shows the concentration curve of the yeast cell cultivation in the course of the whole fermentation. This curve was evaluated with the technique described above. The single points in Figure 7 represent offline probes evaluated with a standard offline microscope cell-counting method. It can be seen that the results of the depth-from-focus technique correspond well to the offline measurement.

During fermentation a slight decrease in cell size with time could be observed. This drift in size causes an error in depth recovery and therefore in concentration

measurements. However this error can be compensated by a correction based on an interpolation of the slope of the volume-concentration profile of the series [Scholz, 1994].

Due to the better illumination in the image center only a centered 128×128 area of interest was selected and processed. For the processing of one image approximately 30-60 seconds CPU time on a fast i860 board are needed. The required time also depends on the cell concentration. Unfortunately this is still a too long calculation time for online measurements at fast fermentation processes with a high dynamical range of concentrations. Therefore we are giving a lot of effort to the development of faster algorithms.

Fig. 7: Evaluated cell concentrations.

6 Conclusions

The introduced depth-from-focus technique is suitable for a wide range of applications. It requires only a single image to obtain the distance between a simple object and the focal plane. Tests with precisely positioned and shifted standard objects showed a very good correspondence between the given and the evaluated distance to the focal plane. The technique has been successfully applied to obtain a virtual measuring volume in which the cell concentration of a fermentation process was evaluated. For optimizing and testing the described method further depth series with standard particles and experimental fermentations were accomplished in May 1994. The evaluation of this series is in progress. Furthermore a better consideration of the cell size increase by a 2-D component ratio -

size calibration field is planned. Since the experiment allows for visualizing single cells, it is intended to draw conclusions on the metabolism of cells by measuring the temporal response of fluorescence during cultivation.

Acknowledgements

This research was financed by the ABB Corporate Research Center Heidelberg which is gratefully acknowledged.

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